

Arthritis Research UK

Data management plan required?	Yes. For some grants there is a 2-stage process - 1 st stage does not require a DMP. Second stage does. For one stage grant such as Connect Immune Research the following is in the guidelines: 'data management and data sharing plans (to include making the data discoverable and the process for data sharing)'
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	research@arthritisresearchuk.org
Comments	Member of AMRC – some grants with links to MRC such as Joint funded MRC clinician scientist fellowship

Documents used:

Information for applicants

www.arthritisresearchuk.org/Research/Information-for-applicants/types-of-grant

Accessed: May 2018